

FORMS AND STAGES OF STUDENTS' INDEPENDENT WORK IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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Abstract: The article covers some aspects of the importance of independent learning improvement and discusses the types and stages of independent work of students. It also deals important requirements for organizing independent work of students. There are many possibilities for young generation today, including lessons at schools, colleges and universities, numerous language courses of different levels, exchange studies university programs, chances to travel to English speaking countries, individual learning or self-studies.

Key words: independent work of students, forms and stages of independent work, methods of organizing independent work of students

1 INTRODUCTION

Communication in this fast-developing world is impossible without learning a foreign language. There are lots of benefits for young people in learning foreign languages and particularly English today. This gives them different opportunities for getting education, doing research, and work abroad. All these in its turn give us as a developed society chances to be aware of everything new in science, industry, politics development of other nations.

Youth today understands the importance of learning English. Over a billion people on the Earth speak English. English is the most studied language in the world, whose influence is so great that it is able to affect not only the dictionary, but also the linguistic structure of the other languages. One of the possible causes of spreading English is the wealth of its vocabulary (about 600 000 words, according to the Oxford dictionary, not counting special technical vocabulary) and a large percent of the international concepts (up to 200 000 words). Here we should add richness synonymous that allows English speakers to distinguish the shades of the meaning. ESP language teaching has much in common with the general language teaching, but at the same time there are specific aspects, which will be presented in this article.

Today aspects of individual teaching and learning are the first and most important consideration in any teaching. The teacher should know exactly what his students are expected to achieve in individual learning of his subject, what changes he can bring about in his students at the end of the course, at the end of the year, term, month, week, and each particular lesson, i.e., he

should know the aims and objectives of ESP language teaching.

With the introduction of the credit module system into the higher education of Uzbekistan every student should clearly understand that the amount of the classroom studies and self-studies equals nowadays. It means that all students take responsibility to provide themselves with the same number of hours that have been spent at university for every subject. This new rule has many advantages. The students have less lectures, they can devote their time to their interests, they should not any longer listen to uninteresting for them lectures or seminars, they can distribute their time more efficiently. For example, they can visit an exciting exhibition daytime and spend time at the library or at home studying their specialty or English in the evening.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

The contemporary system of higher education raises many challenges, the most important of which is to improve the quality of training specialists. The graduate should be creative and fluent not only in his or her specialty, but also be fully conversant in allied domains and willing to continuous professional development, social communicativeness and mobility. It is impossible to solve this problem without increasing the role of independent work of students in the learning process, increasing the responsibility of the teacher for the development of skills of independent work in students and growing their creative activity. The student must not only master the skills and experience of using the knowledge gained from the teacher, but also be able to conduct an independent search for the information he or she needs professionally. Independent work of students is based on the principles of independence, didactic and

creative orientation, goal-oriented planning, person-centered and activity approach.

Forms of independent work of students are various. This includes:

- study and systematization of official state documents - laws, resolutions, decrees, resolutions and instructions and certificates using information retrieval systems;
- study of educational, scientific and methodical literature, materials of periodicals using electronic means of official, statistical, periodical and scientific information;
- preparation of reports and abstracts, solving practical problems, writing term papers and final qualification papers;
- participation in student conferences, comprehensive research. Independent work encourages students to be creative, search and solve actual modern problems.

The main goal of organizing and implementing students' independent work should be consistent with the goal of student education - the preparation of bachelors of higher education. The formation of the ability to work independently is an important and necessary condition for acquiring knowledge, skills and opportunities for organizing educational and scientific activities in the organization of the award.

The purpose of independent work of students is to acquire fundamental knowledge, professional skills and skills in the profile, experience in creative, research activities. Independent work of students contributes to the development of independence, responsibility and organization, a creative approach to solving problems at the educational and professional level. The tasks of the SSR are:

- systematize and consolidate the theoretical knowledge and practical skills of students;
- deepening and expansion of theoretical knowledge;
- to develop the skills of using normative, legal, reference documents and special literature;
- development of knowledge and activity of students: creative initiative, independence, responsibility and organization;
- develop the skills of independent thinking, self-development, self-improvement and self-awareness;
- development of research skills;
- the use of materials collected and received in the process of independent work when writing term papers and theses, qualification documents for effective preparation for final exams.

In the educational process of the university, independent work is distinguished - extracurricular. Extracurricular independent work is carried out by a

student under the guidance of a teacher, but without his direct participation.

The main types of independent work of students without the participation of teachers:

- formation and assimilation of the content of the text of the lecture on the basis of textbooks recommended by the teacher, including educational information resources (electronic textbooks and libraries, etc.);
- writing a dissertation;
- compile an annotated list of articles in relevant journals in the field of knowledge;
- performance of microphotographs;
- preparation of practical developments;
- homework in the form of solving individual problems, performing approximate calculations, individual work on a computer and individual sections of the content of science;
- current computer self-control and control of success based on eLearning and certification tests.

The main types of independent work of students with the participation of teachers:

- regular consultations;
- colloquium as a form of control over the assimilation of the theoretical content of disciplines: (during consultation hours provided for by the curriculum);
- acceptance and analysis of homework (during practical classes);
- implementation of term papers (projects) in subjects (guidance, consulting and defense of term papers (during the hours indicated in the curriculum);
- teaching and research (guidance, counseling and advocacy);
- conducting and processing the results of the internship (management and assessment of the level of formation of professional skills and competencies);
- completion of final works (supervision, consulting and defense of final dissertations), etc.

Methods for organizing students' independent work depend on the structure, nature and characteristics of the topic being studied, the number of hours and its study, the type of tasks for students' independent work, the individual qualities of students and the conditions of educational activity.

3 CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, the process of organizing students' independent work includes the following steps:

- preparation (goal setting, program development, methodological preparation, equipment preparation);
- basic (implementation of the program, use of information retrieval methods, assimilation, processing,

application, transfer of knowledge, determination of results, self-organization of the work process);

- final (assessment and analysis of the significance of the results, their systematization, evaluation of the effectiveness of programs and methods of work, conclusions on the areas of labour optimization).

The organization of independent work of students is provided by universities, educational and methodological departments, teachers, libraries, publishing houses and others.

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